

Table of Contents

Page	Vision Element
1	<u><i>A radical reimagining of the community research paradigm</i></u>
2	<u><i>Authentic, equal, trusting community-academic partnerships</i></u>
3	<u><i>Funding and infrastructure sustainability to enable long-term, extended impact</i></u>
4	<u><i>Strong data and research infrastructure enabling improved rapid response to emerging challenges</i></u>
5	<u><i>Research findings drive meaningful system impact and action</i></u>
6	<u><i>Equitable, holistic care for all</i></u>

In 10 years we see...

A radical reimagining of the community research paradigm

**6 of 8 sessions represented*

What we mean by this is...

- There is a shift from community-based research to **community-driven research**.
 - Communities have autonomy around research: THEY drive the questions, THEY manage and receive the budget, THEY lead the work.
 - De-siloed, de-colonized community engagement. Movement away from “we know what’s best” for communities.
 - Communities are no longer serving the needs of researchers. Researchers exist to be in service to community.
 - The community is the expert of themselves. Their expertise is respected and valued.
- **Systems, structures and processes** for “how research is done” are **radically redesigned** to reflect this paradigm shift.
 - Funding proposals and streams don’t drive research but are driven by community needs.
 - Language and processes are accessible.
 - The timeline and pace of research shifts to be realistic and adaptable to community needs and allow a real exchange of hypothesis, curiosity, and dialogue.
 - We value multiple ways of knowing and different kinds of research design, including rethinking ideas of who can hold leadership and “principal investigator” positions and what that looks like.
 - Research evolves in how it invites participation: who is involved, what motivates participation.

In 10 years we see...

Authentic, equal, trusting community-academic partnerships

**7 of 8 sessions represented*

What we mean by this is...

- **Communities and research work side by side as trusting, co-accountable partners.**
 - There is parity in the relationship between community and academic research.
 - Researchers listen, believe, respect, and value community expertise.
 - There is real exchange of hypotheses, curiosity, dialogue and collaborative problem solving.
 - Less of "us vs them" research approach and more "doing this together."
 - Research doesn't helicopter in from "outside," but is embedded within. Not liaising with the community, but OF the community.
 - The new level of trust present creates an eagerness in the community to be involved in research

- **Learning and capacity building is bi-directional.**
 - The idea of who "needs training" is flipped with researchers being trained to have a deep relationship with the community contexts where they are working.
 - Communities learn from researchers and researchers learn from communities. There is understanding that capacity and training are needed to support the growth and learning of both entities.
 - Community members have access to research information - they are not just a test subject, source for input, or object for study.

In 10 years we see...

Funding and infrastructure sustainability to enable long-term, extended impact

**5 of 8 sessions represented*

What we mean by this is...

- **Funding streams are continuous, accessible, and appropriate** to enable extended impact
 - Firm and steady commitment for funding sustainability that's not reliant on a single source
 - Funding builds on itself. Recipients of funding don't have to reinvent the infrastructure wheel with every stream.
 - Communities and researchers have increased funding opportunities because of their increased collaboration
 - Reliable funding enables the network to broaden areas of focus and impact
- Long term **sustainability of the RADx-UP network**
 - RADx-UP Network is respected and seen as an expert source
 - There is connection maintained between the network of communities doing RADx-UP COVID work so that the network can be easily reactivated for future emerging public health threats
- There is **permanent, established infrastructure at the federal level** for health equity research.

In 10 years we see...

Strong data and research infrastructure enabling improved rapid response to emerging challenges

**5 of 8 sessions represented*

What we mean by this is...

- **Robust and integrated data systems for deeper understanding and predictive insights**
 - **Integrated data systems** and standardized common data elements that allow us to compare among communities, and a comprehensive data hub we can draw on to answer current and future equity questions.
 - **More precise and extensive data** that enables:
 - deeper understanding at a nuanced, community-specific level,
 - predictive insights about emerging patterns,
 - personalized public health and clinical responses.
 - **Labs integrated** alongside communities and academic centers, in order to detect problems and patterns early and be prepared for what might emerge.
- Web of interconnected communities with **seamless, quickly-deployable research infrastructure** (tech, tools, processes, people) in place for rapid response to emergent public health challenges

In 10 years we see...

Research findings driving meaningful system impact and action

**5 of 8 sessions represented*

What we mean by this is...

- **Research has a “fund what you find” approach.** The end result of the research should be the next thing funded to solve.
 - There is money already identified to fund the solution/action that research is designed to identify/incite.
 - This is about acting on the outcomes of research and not abandoning people after they share what they need through the research.
 - Shift away from the “take without giving back” approach to research
- Research findings are translated to **improve public health practice**
 - Implementation science is the standard (promoting the uptake of results into clinical and public health practice)
 - Translation of data from research/lab to clinical care and public health efforts (i.e. learn how to effectively communicate risks, benefits and costs of health behaviors)
 - Research is accessible, transparent, understandable. It is “sticky” for practitioners and the public.
 - Learnings and successes are reapplied to new challenges, rather than a constant “reinventing the wheel”
- Research results drive **public policy shifts** and national level change
 - There is a solid infrastructure that allows improved messaging, funding, policy and agile responsiveness at the national level

- Underlying systemic issues are identified and public policy reflects the changes needed

In 10 years we see...

Equitable, holistic care for all

****7 of 8 sessions represented***

What we mean by this is...

- **Research concerns and topics shift** to reflect an expanded, holistic understanding of "health"
 - Broader Social Determinants of Health are addressed through research, (i.e. more upstream issues such as racism)
 - Other health needs and scientific areas of focus are being addressed by the established infrastructure
 - Mental health
 - Racism
 - Environmental exposures
 - Wealth and justice
 - Etc.
- **Top notch health care is available to all** and people have access to what they need
 - Well-vetted resources that meet community member's health and health care needs.
 - All populations have better access to care (e.g. rural, underserved)
 - RADx-UP research has changed the way that care is delivered to improve access and remove barriers
 - SDoH are addressed, even issues such as broadband connectivity, housing, and transit